

FREQUENCY OF MANIPULATIVE BEHAVIOR OF PARENTS IN THE DIVORCE PROCESS

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***Abstract.** The content of the work is oriented towards the issue of divorce with reference to the frequency of manipulative behavior of parents. Divorce is an event that is on the rise in modern society, and its consequences are far-reaching, both for former spouses and for joint children. Divorce ends a marriage, but it must not be the end of the family, especially when at least one child was born in the marriage. Some parents, in addition to dealing with their emotional reactions to divorce, find ways to provide their child with the support they need. Unfortunately, we also have those parents who do not recognize the child's reactions to divorce and the child remains deprived of the necessary support. Parents often, knowingly or unknowingly, involve children in partner conflicts. The manipulative behavior of parents manifests itself in different ways, such as making it difficult and impossible to meet with the other parent, false accusations of abuse, negative representation of the other parent, and others. Constant cooperation of experts, social workers, psychologists, pedagogues and lawyers can result in problem detection and timely reaction in order to protect children from the consequences of parents' manipulative behavior. Experts who deal with divorce and the consequences it leaves on the child advocate, as the best model, the joint exercise of parental rights after divorce. This would mean that they jointly*

and consensually exercise parental rights, that they have a joint parenting plan and that they agree on all issues related to the child. The research is oriented towards obtaining and analyzing the results in order to identify the problem of manipulation with special reference to its frequency. The increasing frequency of divorce obliges experts to look for preventive solutions to the problem, as well as ways to help ex-spouses and children overcome the problems brought about by divorce in order to minimize the manipulative behavior of parents. Analyzing the results of the research, the manipulative behavior of the parents in relation to the child exists in as many as 50.9%, compared to 49.1 parents who deny this behavior.

Keywords: *Divorce. Frequency of manipulation. Social support. Social work.*

INTRODUCTION

The family is a social institution that influences the destiny of an individual, and for that reason, it is in the sphere of scientific interest. Divorce, as a factor that contributes to the increase in the number of single-parent families, causes a high degree of stress on all its members and can have different and far-reaching consequences on the psychosocial development of children.

Divorce as a very complex psychosocial phenomenon includes individual and partner relationships, but it also reflects on the family as a whole. Divorce implies the termination of the union of legally married partners, but behind it is a complex process that takes place in stages and covers several levels of separation, i.e. the cessation of joint functioning of spouses and other family members. (Polovina, Žegarac, 2005)

The process of divorce takes years in some cases. It starts with arguments and conflicts before the divorce itself, continues during the divorce process and very often after it. The child often does not understand these changes and they reduce the predictability and stability that the family enjoyed until then. A high-conflict divorce implies the possibility of reaching an agreement on certain issues. Preoccupation with mutual partner conflicts can have such proportions that ex-spouses neglect the needs

of the child or start arguing and fighting over everything that concerns the child, convinced that they have to save the child from harm that could be committed by the other parent. When parents who are in a high conflict after divorce are characterized by a high level of hostility followed by malicious mutual accusations against the other parent, thereby involving the child in partnership conflicts, with the aim of obstructing a good relationship with the other parent, we speak of manipulative parenting.

Although some studies talk about the negative consequences of divorce on the child, it is becoming increasingly clear that the child is not harmed by the act of the parents' divorce itself, but by the parental conflict that is often present in all stages of the divorce.

In high-conflict divorces where conflicts between former partners are present, children's rights to the continued development of relations with both parents are violated, even though it is estimated that this is in their best interest. Manipulative behavior is resorted to by both parents through various behavioral, verbal and non-verbal messages that have a negative connotation about the other parent. The goal of these messages is to exclude the parents from the child's life.

A special risk in high-conflict divorces is the alienation of the child from the parents. Alienation is characterized by the behavior of parents who deliberately disrupt the child's relationship with the other parent (Roje Drapić, Buljan Flander, 2019).

The difficulties faced by a child who has gone through the experience of divorce are of a social, economic and health nature. The child's reactions to divorce certainly depend on the length and intensity of the parents' conflict, on the child's age, but also on the way the parents behave towards each other. Exposure to parental conflict, but also involving the child in it, enhances the appearance of psychosocial consequences in children. Some of those consequences are low self-esteem, learning disabilities and poorer school performance, anxiety, fears, and so on.

OBJECTIVE OF THE RESEARCH

The goal of our work is to determine the frequency of manipulative parenting in the divorce process. In the introductory part, we looked at the issue of high-conflict divorce and the consequences that such a divorce brings with it. When the manipulative behavior of the parents is present in the divorce process, the problem becomes even more complicated and requires special attention from experts as well as the protection of children in order to minimize the consequences on their psychophysical development. Research aimed at determining the frequency of manipulative parenting in the divorce process, as well as the most common forms of it, can contribute to the development of strategies to prevent or solve problems of this type that have already arisen. We conducted the research in Serbia, on the territory of the Municipality of Zrenjanin, including respondents from urban and suburban areas. Through the analysis, we obtained the results of the research that was conducted among respondents, mothers and fathers, who went through the experience of divorce and at least one child was born in the marriage. The research included 55 respondents, of which 34 were female and 21 were male.

RESEARCH METHOD

For our research, we have chosen a quantitative research method. The questionnaire is self-constructed, anonymous, and the parents' answers will give us a broader picture of the problem of the frequency of manipulative parenting. Guided by the set goal, which is to determine the frequency of occurrence of manipulative behavior of parents, we will present the obtained results in tables. We will analyze respondents' answers to 10 research questions.

INTERPRETATION OF RESEARCH RESULTS

Question number 1:

Degree of your education?

Table 1. Distribution of respondents in relation to the acquired education

LEVEL OF EDUCATION	NUMBER OF RESPONDENTS	EXPRESSED IN %
PRIMARY SCHOOL	7	12,7
SECONDARY SCHOOL	26	47,3
HIGHER PROFESSIONAL DEGREE OR MASTER'S DEGREE	22	40

In relation to the acquired education, by analyzing the obtained data, we obtained the following results: the largest number of respondents has an acquired secondary professional education 47.3%, followed by respondents who have completed a higher vocational education or master's degree 40% and finally respondents who have completed basic education 12.7%.

Question number 2:

How did your marriage end?

Table 2. Distribution of respondents in relation to the way the marriage ended

METHOD OF TERMINATION OF MARRIAGE	NUMBER OF RESPONDENTS	EXPRESSED IN %
LAW FOR DIVORCE OF MARRIAGE	24	43,6
CONSENT DIVORCE	31	56,4

To the research question asked, which refers to the manner in which the marriage was terminated, the respondents were offered two answers, the termination of the marital union through a lawsuit for divorce and the consensual divorce. Out of a total of 55 respondents, 24 respondents answered that their marriage was ended by a lawsuit, and the other 31 respondents said that their marriage was ended by agreement.

Question number 3:

How to exercise parental rights after divorce?

Table 3. The schedule of respondents in relation to the way of exercising parental rights after divorce

METHOD OF EXERCISE OF PARENTAL RIGHTS AFTER DIVORCE	NUMBER OF RESPONDENTS	EXPRESSED IN %
INDEPENDENT EXERCISE OF PARENTAL RIGHTS	35	63,6
JOINT EXERCISE OF PARENTAL RIGHTS	20	36,4

The results obtained for this research question are as follows: after divorce, 35 respondents, or 63.6% of respondents, exercise parental rights independently, while 20 respondents, or 36.4%, exercise parental rights jointly.

Question number 4:

How often have your children witnessed marital disputes?

Table 4. Distribution of respondents according to the frequency of children's presence in marital disputes

FREQUENCY OF MARITAL DISPUTES	NUMBER OF RESPONDENTS	EXPRESSED IN %
SOMETIMES	22	40
OFTEN	19	34,5
NEVER	14	25,5

Research question number 4, which refers to the frequency of the presence of children in marital disputes, respondents were offered three answers to which they gave their answers in the following percentage: As an answer, sometimes, 40% of respondents circled, 34.5 often circled % and "never", 25.5% of respondents.

Question number 5:

How is your communication with your ex-partner after the divorce?

Table 5. Display of communication with ex-partner after divorce

COMMUNICATION WITH A FORMER PARTNER	NUMBER OF RESPONDENTS	EXPRESSED IN %
WE HAVE NO COMMUNICATION	10	18,18
COMMUNICATION IS BAD	11	20
COMMUNICATION IS GOOD	19	34,55
WE ONLY COMMUNICATE THROUGH CHILDREN	15	27,27

Respondents could give one of 4 answers to this research question. 18.18% of respondents answered that they have no communication with their ex-partner. 20% of respondents answered that he has bad communication. 34.55% of respondents have good communication after divorce, and 27.27% communicate only through their children.

Question number 6:

What is the relationship of the child after the divorce with the parent with whom he does not live?

Statement A., The child should choose which side he will be on, that is, who he will be loyal to,,

Table 6. The child's relationship with the other parent after the divorce

DEGREE OF AGREEMENT	EXPRESSED IN %
I DO NOT AGREE AT ALL	20
I DO NOT AGREE	20
I'M NOT SURE	14,55
I AGREE	34,55
I TOTALLY AGREE	10,9

Statement B. "I don't prevent the relationship with the other parent, but I don't promote it either."

Table 7. The child's relationship with the other parent after the divorce

DEGREE OF AGREEMENT	EXPRESSED IN %
I DO NOT AGREE AT ALL	12,73
I DO NOT AGREE	9,09
I'M NOT SURE	16,37
I AGREE	41,81
I TOTALLY AGREE	20

Statement C "After the divorce, constructive co-parenting should be advocated."

Table 8. The child's relationship with the other parent after the divorce

DEGREE OF AGREEMENT	EXPRESSED IN %
I DO NOT AGREE AT ALL	10,9
I DO NOT AGREE	5,46
I'M NOT SURE	27,27
I AGREE	32,7
I TOTALLY AGREE	23,67

Statement D. "Encouraging contact with the ex-partner's extended family is not in the best interest of the child."

Table 9. The child's relationship with the other parent after the divorce

DEGREE OF AGREEMENT	EXPRESSED IN %
I DO NOT AGREE AT ALL	20
I DO NOT AGREE	34,55
I'M NOT SURE	27,27
I AGREE	9,09
I TOTALLY AGREE	9,09

This research question was presented in the form of a five-point Likert scale. This scale contains four statements concerning the child's co-parent relationship after divorce.

Question number 7:

Is your ex-partner trying to win the child over to his care by various means?

Table 10. Presentation of the existence of the parent's manipulative behavior in relation to the child

THE EXISTENCE OF MANIPULATIVE PROCEDURES	EXPRESSED IN %
YES	50,9
NOT	49,1

Respondents could give two types of answers to this research question: Yes or No. Respondents who answered in the affirmative should have supplemented their answer with an explanation of what those procedures were. Out of the total number of respondents, 28 respondents answered yes to this question, while 27 answered no. Out of the total affirmative answers, 26 respondents gave an explanation, while two respondents left this column empty. Some respondents indicated one form of manipulative behavior of the ex-partner as an answer, while some respondents indicated two or three forms of manipulative behavior of the parents. The most common responses of respondents who gave answers to these questions are:

The ex-partner tells the child all the worst about the other parent.

- Telling lies about life together in order to gain a child
- Bribing, manipulating money, buying anything the child wants
- Making false promises
- Inconsistent upbringing - the opposite of the upbringing of the other parent
- Preventing meeting with the other parent
- Represents the child of the other parent as the sole culprit for the divorce
- Lack of interest in upbringing and contact with the child

Question number 8:

How long did the divorce proceedings last in your case?

Table 11. Presentation of the duration of the divorce proceedings

NUMBER OF RESPONDENTS DURATION OF DIVORCE PROCEEDINGS	DURATION OF DIVORCE PROCEEDINGS
24	1-3 months
16	4-6 months
4	6-9 months
3	9-12 months
8	More than a year

Question number 9:

Did your social worker offer you the possibility to participate in some counseling procedure in order to avoid difficulties during the divorce proceedings?

Table 12. Presentation of respondents in relation to the offered possibility of inclusion in the counseling procedure in the divorce process

	NUMBER OF RESPONDENTS	EXPRESSED IN %
No, I was not offered such an opportunity	31	56,4
Yes, I was offered such an opportunity	24	43,6

Question number 10:

Have your children been offered expert treatment, counseling or psychological support during the divorce proceedings?

Table 13. Presentation of respondents in relation to the support provided to children by experts

	NUMBER OF RESPONDENTS	EXPRESSED IN %
Da	12	21,8
Ne	43	78,2

DISCUSSION OF RESEARCH RESULTS

When parents divorce, children are in a very disadvantageous position, because they depend on their parents and the divorce itself is out of their control. They cannot see the course and duration of the divorce as well as what its outcome will be. Children often lack information and skills to overcome this difficult situation (Žakula Desnica, 2010). Divorce is an extremely stressful experience for every child, which causes strong emotional reactions in him. Parents who themselves survive the divorce violently, struggling with their own emotions and losses, are not able to provide the child with much-needed support. In such situations, the child's needs, his emotional reactions to the parents' conflict, remain unrecognized and the child is deprived of much-needed support. (Filipović, Osmak-Franić, 2010).

Research question number four, which refers to the presence of children in marital disputes, the answers of our respondents indicate that 74.5% of children often or sometimes attended marital disputes. Tamara Žakula, right-winger, in her work "Poor-quality divorce and manipulation of children", states a similar result, which is that 71% of children witnessed parental verbal conflicts. Branka Čavarović Gabor, in her work entitled, Divorce of parents and symptoms of trauma in children, on page 74 (2008) states, Exposure to parental conflicts causes children of all ages to experience emotional and behavioral problems.

In the description of the communication of former partners after the divorce, 34.55% of the respondents state that they have good communication, and 64.45% of the respondents state that they have poor communication, no communication at all or

communicate through their children. In her book, *Divorce and What About the Children*, Lynn Evans says that one of the most harmful practices of divorcing parents is to use children as messengers. For constructive co-parenting after divorce, it is necessary to ignore disagreements and continue good cooperation on child-rearing issues. Macoby and Mnookin conducted a longitudinal study regarding the presence or absence of communication and agreement on issues related to a joint child, they came to similar results: 35% of respondents have strong communication, while 65% of respondents have weak communication (Profaca, 2010). The presentation of the level of communication between former partners is aimed at understanding this issue and finding new ways of family and individual interventions.

„Family members in two-way family communication express emotions and share information, and if there are problems in communication, they often prefer negative styles of interaction" (Mlinarević, 2022, p. 136).

In a situation where the parental conflict continues after the divorce and makes it difficult for the child to adapt to the new situation and disrupts the relationship with the other parent, we must think about appropriate forms of support for the parents after the divorce, which are based on the elements of empowerment and understanding of the parental conflict (Urbanc, 2020).

Further analyzing the results of the research, the sixth research question, which was offered in the form of statements and concerns the child's relationship with the other parent after the divorce, we obtained the following results: with statement number 1, „The child should choose which side he will be on, that is, who he will be loyal to „45.45% of respondents completely agree or agree, 40% of respondents completely disagree or disagree, while 14.55% of respondents gave the answer that they are not sure. If we consider that the conflict of loyalty has an extremely negative effect on the well-being of children, a percentage of 45.45% says that the problem is not negligible.

„Divorce is a period of conflict of loyalty for children, which parents can intensify with their mutual struggle for the child.,(Laklija et. al, 2005, p. 7).

The statement "I do not prevent the relationship with the other parent but I do not promote it either", the percentage of representation with 61.81% does not prevent the relationship but does not promote it either, 21.82% completely disagree, while 16.37% are not sure.

The statement, After the divorce, constructive co-parenting should be advocated, 56.37% of respondents fully agree or agree, 16.36% disagree with this statement and 27.27% are not sure. When it comes to the last statement from our questionnaire, Encouraging contact with the extended family of the ex-partner is not in the best interest of the child, 18.18% of respondents completely agree or agree, 54.55% do not agree at all or do not agree while 27.27% it's not sure. Analyzing these results, we can conclude that the manipulative influence of parents is present in many forms. A large percentage of the respondents agree that the involvement of both parents in the child's life after divorce should be enabled, that constructive joint parenting should be advocated, as well as encouraging the child's contact with the extended family of the ex-partner. However, when it comes to sending negative messages, preventing the meeting of the child and the ex-partner, putting the child in a situation to choose who will be loyal but does not improve the relationship with the other parent, about 50% of respondents - Gordana Filipović and Davora Osmak Franjić in their work related to The manipulative interference of parents in the divorce process shows the data obtained by the research that during the divorce in 30% of cases, the child's right to meet and socialize with both parents is manipulated, which further results in preventing the child's right to develop communication. These results indicate the need for timely intervention in mediation between parents in the divorce process. In her research, Milana Ljubičić found that the protection of children by the other parent when the child's behavior is inappropriate exists in 31% of cases. As another form of manipulation, the author states that offering a coalition to a child exists in 25.2% of cases. Comparing the results of our research with the research of Milana Ljubičić, we conclude that the manipulative behavior of parents in the divorce process exists in a high percentage and in various forms.

Regardless of the circumstances, parents are expected to know the characteristics of children's development, to be able to establish quality family relationships, and to apply appropriate educational procedures (Pintar, 2019).

Presentation of the duration of the divorce procedure: 43.64% of the respondents said that the divorce lasted for a period of 3 months, 29.09% for a period of 6 months, and the remaining 27.27% of the respondents said that the divorce lasted for a year or more. Due to the specificity of this issue, we are of the opinion that the shorter duration of divorce proceedings reduces the space for the development of manipulative parenting.

The question related to support for parents and children by experts in CSW aimed at mapping institutional responses to the problem of manipulative parenting. Based on the results obtained, when it came to support for parents, more than half of the parents answered that there was no such possibility. And when it comes to children, the situation is even more alarming, as many as 72.8% of respondents answered that such an opportunity was not offered to their children. Marina Hugson is in your book, *Too much responsibility, too little support*, 2015. on page 87 states, *"Most of the interviewed parents have limited experience with CSW, and if it could be expected that their need for contacts is much greater. Experiences are mostly neutral or even negative,,*

Danka Radulović and Natalija Iignjtović in their work, *Assessment of the negative consequences of divorce on minor children and possible interventions*, state that numerous interventions have been developed with the aim of helping children in situations when their parents divorce. When it comes to checking their effectiveness, we do not have an extensive examination of the direct impact on children's adjustment. Valid evaluation studies highlight the beneficial effects of interventions aimed at reducing parental conflicts, improving the child's relationship with parents, improving parental competencies, and supporting children in schools.

CONCLUSION

Divorce is traumatic for the whole family, but parents must still be responsible for a quality relationship with their children even in such a difficult situation. Children who have faced the divorce of their parents show different emotional and behavioral problems. A well-ended marriage could be a new type of relationship between family members, and the child would not be deprived of much-needed support. In order to overcome the problems that this phenomenon brings with it, it is necessary to take into account all its consequences and amortize them in the best possible way. An explanation of the divorce in accordance with the age of the child, avoiding conflict in front of the child, not manipulating them, making the availability of both parents available to them, and providing help in overcoming possible self-accusation would ease the situation for the children. It is the duty of parents to continue being parents to their children even after the dissolution of the marriage union.

We are of the opinion that certain progress can be achieved through the active participation of relevant institutions, organizations and individuals in the social protection system, cooperating in the common interest of establishing a quality system of support and protection for the family that is falling apart. to compromise solutions that will be in the best interest of the children as well as the parents themselves.

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